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Clinical Study Of Efficacy Of Pashanbhed Choorna (Bhavprakash) In The Management Of Mutrashmri.

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Abstract

This study deals with evaluation of efficacy of *Pashanbhed Choorna* in the management of *Mutrashmari*. The main aim of this particular study was to report the fast acting and cheapest *Ayurvedic* medicine for *Mutrashmari*. Study was done in 55 patients who were suffering from *Mutrashmari*. Drug *Pashanbhed Choorna* was given to patients in dose of 3 gms twice a day in *Apankala* (After food) with *Koshnajal* as *Anupana*. Study period was of 60 days. The patients were assessed on the basis of subjective parameters i.e. *Udarshool*, *Dahayukta Mutrapavrutti*, *Muhurmuhu Mutrapavrutti* and objective parameters i.e. USG Abdomen & pelvis. The result was satisfactory.

Keywords: *Ayurveda*, *Mutrashmari*, *Pashanbhed Choorna*

Introduction:

There are four types of *Mutrashmari* according to *Shushruta Samhita* i.e. *Vataja*, *Pittaja*, *Shleshmaja* and *Shukraj Ashmari* and according to modern science there are few types of renal calculi i.e. Uric acid, calcium oxalate, calcium phosphate, calcium carbonate, cystine, tyrosine. *Mutrashmari* is one among the eight *Mahagadas*. The reason for considering this disease as *Mahagada* is that, the disease is *Tridoshaja*, *Marmashrayee* and its *Vyaktasthana* is *Basti* which is one among *Dashavidha Pranayatana*. Also sometimes, it is fatal and it may need surgical intervention. The incidence of *Mutrashmari* is rising day by day around the world. It is affecting younger population too. The first step we need to take is to bring changes in diet and lifestyle patterns. Most *Mutrashmari* can be treated without surgery.

In modern science; there are many treatment modalities for urinary calculus like extra corporeal shock wave lithotripsy (ESWL), Percutaneous Nephro Lithotomy (PCNL), URS & Laser etc. having their own merits and demerits. All these procedures reduce the rate of open surgery in urolithiasis. But these procedures are very costly and limited to urban areas only. There are many medicines described by *Ayurved Samhitas*, which are greatly effective on *Mutrashmari*. *Pashanbhed Choorna* is one of the drug explained by *Acharya Bhavprakash*. This drug can be given on O.P.D. basis and is administered without requiring hospitalization. This is a non-invasive and safe drug therapy.

Aim and Objectives- To evaluate efficacy of *Pashanbhed Choorna* with respect to Size of Renal calculus, symptoms like *Udarshool*, *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti*, *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti*.

Material And Method:

No. of patients- 55 Patients
 Drug- *Pashanbhed Choorna*
 Duration of Study- 60 days
 Dose- 3 gm twice a day
 Route of administration- Oral
Anupan- *Koshna jal* 100ml
Kala- *Apankal*
 centre of study- *Ayurved Mahavidyalaya* and Seth R.V. *Ayurved Hospital sion* Mumbai, 22.

Follow Up:

Clinical follow up was advised as:-

- 1st follow up 15th day
- 2nd follow up 30th day
- 3rd follow up 45th day
- 4th follow up 60th day

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patient of *Mutrashmari* presenting with *Udarshool*, *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti*, *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti* of *Mutrashmari* as per classics.
2. Patients between the age group of 18-60 years were selected irrespective of occupation, religion and socio-economic status.
3. Patients having size of calculi upto 15 mm.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Patient having calculi size above 15mm.
2. Patients age below 18 years and above 60 years.
3. Patient having *Mutrashmari* associated with Acute and Chronic kidney failure, undergoing Chemotherapy, Radiation therapy, major operative procedures and pregnancy. Patients presenting with obstructing renal calculi leading to hydronephrosis.

Drug-Pashanbhed Choorna :

Sr. No.	Sanskrit Name	Botanical Name	Proportion
1	<i>Pashanbhed</i>	<i>Bergenia ligulata</i>	1 Part

Preparation of Pashanbhed Choorna Material for Choorna :

Aushadhi Dravya - Dry Choorna of *Pashanbhed*.

Procedure- *Pashanbhed Choorna* was mixed properly and packed into packets.

Assessment Criteria :

Subjective Parameter- Classical sign and symptoms of *Mutrashmari* were considered under subjective parameters and for assessment of overall effect of therapy.

- a. *Udarshool* (Pain in abdomen)
- b. *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti* (Burning micturition)
- c. *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti* (Dribbling micturition)

Objective Parameter- Size of calculus (Determined by USG-abdomen and pelvis) Objective data was analyzed by using "z test" and subjective data were analyzed by using "Mann - Whitney-Wilcoxon U- Test."

Gradation For Subjective Parameters:

In *Udarshool* (pain in abdomen) grade 0 for No pain, grade 1 for intermittent pain, grade 2 for more frequent pain, relieved with oral drugs and grade 3 for Excruciating pain, requiring parental drugs. In *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti* (Burning micturition) grade 0 for no burning micturition, grade 1 for mild, grade 2 for moderate and grade 3 for severe burning micturition. In *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti* (Dribbling micturition) grade 0 for no dribbling micturition, grade 1 for mild, grade 2 for moderate and grade 3 for severe dribbling micturition.

3. Assessment of *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti*-

Statistical Analysis :

1. Assessment of *Udarshool*-

	<i>Udarshool</i> -BT	<i>Udarshool</i> - AT
Type of Scale	Categorical -Ordinal	
Sample Size (n)	55	55
Mean ± SD	2.58 ± 0.60	1.05 ± 0.70
Median	3	1
Range	01 to 03	00 to 02
Statistical Test applied	Mann -Whitney-Wilcoxon U-Test (Large Sample)	
	Mann -Whitney-Wilcoxon	
P-Value	The two-tailed P-value is 0 <0.05 at 5% of level of significance, considered extremely significant.	
Inference	There is significant effect in <i>Udarshool</i> after the treatment.	

2. Assessment of *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti*-

	<i>Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti</i> -BT	<i>Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti</i> -AT
Type of Scale	Categorical -Ordinal	
Sample Size (n)	55	55
Mean ± SD	2.38 ± 0.62	0.89 ± 0.63
Median	2	1
Range	01 to 03	00 to 02
Statistical Test applied	Mann -Whitney-Wilcoxon U-Test (Large Sample)	
	Mann -Whitney-Wilcoxon U-Test Statistic = 9.0108	
P-Value	The two-tailed P-value is 0 <0.05 at 5% of level of significance, considered extremely significant.	
Inference	There is significant effect in <i>Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti</i> after the treatment.	

	<i>Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti</i> -BT	<i>Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti</i> -AT
Type of Scale	Categorical -Ordinal	
Sample Size (n)	55	55
Mean ± SD	1.47 ± 0.63	0.69 ± 0.57
Median	1	1
Range	00 to 03	00 to 02
Statistical Test applied	Mann -Whitney-Wilcoxon U-Test (Large Sample)	
	Mann -Whitney-Wilcoxon U-Test Statistic = 8.0719	
P-Value	The two-tailed P-value is 0 < 0.05 at 5% of level of significance, considered extremely significant.	
Inference	There is significant effect in <i>Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti</i> after the treatment.	

4. Assessment of patients based on size of Calculi-

Size	Mean	N	SD	SE	Z-Value	P-Value
BT	5.66	55	1.921051	0.259034	5.6608	0
AT	3.67	55	3.047113	0.410873		

Discussion:

In *Ayurvedic* literature, various drugs described for treatment of *Mutrashmari*, in which *Pooshanbhed Choorna* was selected the median score of *Udarshool* before treatment was 03 (range 01 to 03) which has got changed to 1 (range 00 to 02). The improvement in *Udarshool* On 60 days of treatment with *Pashanbhed Choorna* was found to be statistically significant. The median score of *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti* before treatment was 2 (range 01 to 03) which has got changed to 1 (range 00 to 02). The improvement in *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti* on 60 days of treatment with *Pashanbhed Choorna* was found to be statistically significant. The median score of *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti* before treatment was 01 (range 01 to 03) which has got changed to 01 (range 00 to 02).

The improvement in *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti* on 60 days of treatment with *Pashanbhed Choorna* was found to be statistically significant. There were 55 patients enrolled in which before treatment mean calculi size was 5.66mm which reduced to 3.67mm. *Pashanbhed Choorna* have *Bhedan* property. *Mutrala* activities of *Pashanbhed Choorna* by *Sheeta Virya* either promote or increase the amount of urine excretion and helps in preventing the Hyper-concentration of urine as well as further complications.

Conclusion :

At the end of the study, it can be concluded that, *Pashanbhed Choorna* is effective in relieving all symptoms of *Mutrashmari* such as *Udarshool*, *Dahayukta Mutrapravrutti*, *Muhurmuhu Mutrapravrutti* as well as reduction in size of *Mutrashmari*.

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